

Using paleomagnetic observations and geodynamo simulations to assess Earth's magnetic field morphology and variability

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Abstract Multiple strategies have been suggested for quantitatively comparing numerical dynamo simulations to geomagnetic field models and paleomagnetic observations. Observationally-constrained metrics are designed to infer properties of simulations that are required to produce Earth-like behaviour and enable inferences on otherwise inaccessible properties of the geomagnetic field, such as its long-term spatio-temporal behaviour at the core-mantle boundary. However, these criteria are derived from data spanning differing timescales with fundamentally different spatio-temporal resolution, are often applied in isolation, and may not be independent assessments, so that holistic syntheses of simulated and observed field variations are currently lacking. In this work, we apply 14 existing criteria measuring field morphological and variability properties on centennial to million-year timescales to a database of 207 dynamos. Individual metrics are matched over various ranges of core-mantle boundary dipolarity (f_d) and its temporal variability (δf_d), though no single range conforms with all proposed metrics. The greatest overlap between simulations matching disparate criteria occurs for $f_d = 0.50 - 0.64$, which is substantially lower than the modern field value of 0.71. Earth-like dynamos tend to have magnetic/kinetic energy ratio >1 , consistent with a MAC force balance, and require a magnetic Reynolds number $Rm = 750 - 1200$ to match the secular variation timescale. Simulations in our dataset exhibit reduced temporal variability at moderate dipolarity ($f_d \sim 0.5$) compared to inferences from global field models, which hinders their capacity to produce Earth-like polarity reversals.

Non-technical summary Numerical geodynamo simulations model the generation of Earth's magnetic field by solving the fundamental physical equations that describe fluid motion and electromagnetism in the outer core. To assess how Earth-like these simulations are, researchers compare them with observations from data-based geomagnetic field models and paleomagnetic records using a range of published metrics. These criteria examine different aspects of geomagnetic behaviour, draw on different types of observations, and span timescales from decades to millions of years. In this study, we apply 14 such criteria to 207 simulations to evaluate both the structure of the magnetic field and how it changes over time. A key property that influences whether simulations meet the criteria is the dipole's strength relative to the total large-scale field at the core surface ('dipolarity'). We find that no single region of parameter space satisfies all metrics simultaneously, and that metrics based on the modern field typically favour a stronger dipolarity than those derived from longer term paleomagnetic data. Some criteria do not effectively discriminate simulations that produce Earth-like behaviour. Simulations show less variability at moderate dipolarity than inferred from geomagnetic field reconstructions, which may help explain why they struggle to produce realistic magnetic polarity reversals.

1 Introduction

Earth's magnetic field provides an important geophysical probe of the deep Earth over geological time (Tarduno et al., 2010; Biggin et al., 2011; Constable and Korte, 2015; Davies et al., 2022). The predominant component of the magnetic field at Earth's surface is generated from the turbulent motion of liquid metal in Earth's outer core. This dipole-dominated 'main field' is known to have changed on a vast

range of temporal and spatial scales, from long-period variations in the frequency of polarity reversals to rapid geomagnetic jerks (Gallet et al., 2009; Brown et al., 2013; Constable and Constable, 2023) and "spikes" in field strength (Shaar et al., 2017; Davies and Constable, 2017) and direction (Davies and Constable, 2020; Constable and Davies, 2024). On centennial to multi-millennial timescales the field exhibits striking changes in morphology and variability, including reversals and excursions that are sampled by globally distributed datasets. The recent proliferation of field models

Handling Editor:
Mathieu Dumberry
Received:
March 23, 2026
Revised:
May 8, 2026
Accepted:
June 1, 2026
Published:
June 12, 2026

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spanning various parts of the last 10 Ma (Constable et al., 2016; Cromwell et al., 2018; Campuzano et al., 2019; Korte et al., 2019; Panovska et al., 2019; Panovska et al., 2021; Nilsson et al., 2022; Mahgoub et al., 2023) presents the opportunity to interrogate the physics underpinning observed field behaviour by comparisons with numerical simulations of the dynamo process that generates the field. Here we seek to establish the level of quantitative agreement between outputs from field models and numerical simulations spanning centennial to million-year timescales.

Spherical harmonics offer a compact and physically meaningful global representation of the radial magnetic field B_r through the Gauss coefficients $g_{l,m}$ and $h_{l,m}$, defined at Earth's surface for degree l and order m . This formulation enables direct comparison with surface and satellite observations, as well as with their temporal evolution. Spherical harmonics constitute the standard basis for the inversion of global, time-dependent geomagnetic field models derived from observational data and are also easily obtained from numerical geodynamo simulations. Consequently, they provide a unifying framework for evaluating standard geomagnetic elements and a broad range of derived quantities, thereby establishing their statistical properties. In paleofield studies, data coverage is often limited and global geomagnetic field models are unavailable prior to 100 ka (except for selected polarity changes, e.g. Mahgoub et al., 2023; Lanci et al., 2008), but derived statistics can still be computed directly from observations and compared to simulation outputs. Establishing the level of agreement between simulated and observed magnetic field behaviour spanning centennial to million-year timescales requires criteria that can be estimated with the variable spatio-temporal resolution afforded by available observations and that quantify the established range of field behaviour; from the detailed morphology and time-dependence that can be resolved on centennial timescales to longer-term Paleosecular Variation (PSV) including excursions and reversals. The overall aim is to infer the unobservable dynamics and the physical state of the core that are compatible with geomagnetic field observations assessed through appropriate criteria.

On decadal timescales, satellite and full-vector observatory data enable estimation of the instantaneous rate of change of the radial field \dot{B}_r . Together with B_r it is then possible to construct a timescale τ_l for field changes as a function of spherical harmonic degree l . Lhuillier et al. (2011) showed that $\tau_l = \tau_{SV}/l$ for the large-scale poloidal non-dipole field measured by models of the modern geomagnetic field. Christensen and Tilgner (2004) and Christensen et al. (2012) further showed that τ_{SV} varies as the inverse of the magnetic Reynolds number Rm , the ratio of magnetic induction to diffusion. This relationship has been verified in subsequent studies (Amit et al., 2018; Aubert et al., 2025).

Over historical to Holocene (present–11.7 ka) timescales, the geomagnetic field at the core-mantle boundary (CMB) is dominated by an axial dipole, while the non-dipolar field is primarily equatorially antisymmetric, manifesting as non-zonal patches of high-latitude magnetic flux that are generally located just outside the inner-core tangent cylinder (e.g. Jackson et al., 2000; Constable et al., 2016). These field features have been quantified using spherical harmonic models in terms of the dipolarity (f_d), ratio of axial dipole to non-axial-dipole field (A_N), zonal to non-zonal (Z_N) and odd

to even parity spherical harmonic (O_E) contributions, and flux concentration (F_C) (collectively termed compliance criteria; Christensen et al., 2010), as well as preferred locations of intense flux patches (Mound et al., 2015). From a large dataset of dynamo models ($N = 155$), Christensen et al. (2010) suggested that simulated fields compliant with observational constraints on A_N , O_E , Z_N and F_C arise in a wedge-shaped region of $E/Pm - Rm$ parameter space, where E is the Ekman number and Pm is the magnetic Prandtl number. This implies that simulation parameters should be chosen to ensure a geophysically realistic ordering of rotation, magnetic advection, and magnetic diffusion timescales. However, subsequent studies have shown that accessing the wedge-shaped parameter space is not sufficient to ensure simulations reproduce the geomagnetic field morphology according to the criteria of Christensen et al. (2010). Nakagawa and Davies (2022) argued that simulations that pass the compliance criteria, have an Earth-like Rm , and an average magnetic to kinetic energy ratio $E_m/E_k > 1$, indicative of the geophysically-relevant strong-field regime (Schwaiger et al., 2019b), are characterised by a dipolarity in the range $0.35 \leq f_d \leq 0.75$, though simulations which do not pass the compliance criteria also exist in this f_d range.

On 10 – 100 kyr timescales the reduced spatio-temporal resolution afforded by available observations coupled with distinct field behaviour not recorded in the Holocene (present–11.7 ka) necessitates the use of different types of criteria. In particular, quantities such as f_d cannot be accurately estimated from observations and must be inferred. The PSV index P_i (Panovska and Constable, 2017) quantifies instantaneous deviations of the field from an axial dipole based on the virtual dipole moment V and Virtual Geomagnetic Pole (VGP) colatitude. Mason et al. (2024) used 20 dynamo simulations with Earth-like Rm (~ 1000) and $E_m/E_k > 1$ and found that P_i is inversely related to f_d and did not vary systematically with a number of other dynamo control parameters and diagnostics. They found simulated P_i consistent with that of GGF100k in a limited range $0.4 \leq f_d \leq 0.5$, much lower than the value $f_d = 0.71$ that can be calculated directly for the modern field.

On million-year timescales statistical approaches are needed to synthesize paleomagnetic data. Sprain et al. (2019) proposed the Q_{PM} criteria based on the maximum inclination anomaly (ΔI) relative to Geocentric Axial Dipole (GAD) directions, variability of V , VGP dispersion (S), and the fraction of time spent in a transitional state (τ_t). Meduri et al. (2021) found that misfit between simulated and observed Q_{PM} values varied systematically with f_d and was minimised in the range $0.36 \leq f_d \leq 0.56$, again significantly below the modern dipolarity. From a suite of 50 simulations Meduri et al. (2021) found that only those forced at the bottom of the core (instead of in the volume) and with $E < 10^{-3}$ presented low Q_{PM} misfits. Subsequently Biggin et al. (2020) showed that the ratio A_N is inversely correlated with equatorial VGP dispersion, providing a proxy for estimating axial dipole dominance in deep time.

The above criteria have been developed independently to serve specific purposes and tested against disparate simulation datasets, often in isolation. This has led to numerous inferences relating a range of dynamo parameters and diagnostics (e.g. Rm , E_m/E_k , E/Pm , f_d) to properties of simulated fields that are considered Earth-like (e.g. Christensen et al.,

2010; Davies and Constable, 2014; Sprain et al., 2019; Aubert et al., 2025). However, it is presently unclear how a standardised set of simulations perform against a wide range of criteria, which criteria are useful for distinguishing simulations with different setups (e.g. control parameters, boundary conditions, mode of convective driving), and which model properties best capture the level of agreement between simulated and observed magnetic fields. It is also the case that some criteria are not independent, so we might expect some correlations and redundancy and even mutual incompatibility owing to the heterogeneous quality and abundance of the data on which they are evaluated.

In this work we explore a large and consistent database of numerical dynamo simulations run using the Leeds Dynamo Code (Section 2). In Section 3 we define the metrics introduced above and discuss the ranges that have been proposed based on paleomagnetic observations. In Section 4 we evaluate the simulation dataset against each criterion individually and seek to classify simulations that pass each criterion in terms of Rm , f_d , and E_m/E_k . Based on this analysis we consider in Section 5 how simulations simultaneously match a reduced set of criteria, classified depending on f_d and its temporal variability. Discussion and conclusions are presented in Section 6.

2 Overview of simulations

We considered 207 numerical dynamo simulations run with the Leeds Dynamo code (as described in Willis et al., 2007; Davies et al., 2011). Details of the simulations are contained in the table within the supplementary materials, which provides links to the original publications where more information can be found, and so only a brief summary is given here. Simulations solve the Boussinesq equations of the magneto-hydrodynamic dynamo in a spherical shell rotating with angular velocity Ω about the vertical axis. In all simulations gravity varies linearly with radius r in the spherical coordinate system (r, θ, ϕ) (θ is colatitude, and ϕ longitude) and the ratio of inner to outer boundary radii is 0.35 as in modern Earth. The main dimensionless control parameters are the Ekman number $E = \nu/(\Omega D^2)$, the magnetic Prandtl number $Pm = \nu/\eta$, and the Prandtl number $Pr = \nu/\kappa$. Here ν is the fluid viscosity, D the shell thickness, κ is the codensity diffusivity, and η is the magnetic diffusivity. A Rayleigh number Ra measuring the strength of the buoyancy must also be prescribed, with its precise definition depending on the thermochemical boundary conditions and driving mode.

All simulations employ no-slip mechanical boundary conditions with an insulating upper boundary on which a fixed codensity flux is imposed. At the inner boundary 191 of the simulations have an insulating inner core (the remaining 16 using a conducting inner core) while 164 simulations use a fixed codensity flux (the remaining 43 using fixed codensity). The inner boundary conditions are always homogeneous while at the outer boundary the codensity flux can vary laterally. 132 simulations employ a homogeneous outer boundary codensity flux while 66 use a codensity flux pattern inferred from widely used seismic tomography models (Masters et al., 1996; Masters et al., 2000) (with lateral variations ranging from 0.13-10.7 times the mean) and 9 use a spherical harmonic recumbent Y_2^0 pattern (with lateral variations ranging from 0.37-1.82 times the mean). Further details are in the

Supplementary Table. In terms of the radial buoyancy distribution, 18 simulations are purely basally driven (mimicking compositional convection), 48 are purely volumetrically driven (with a constant internal source, as a proxy for secular cooling), and 140 are driven by equal flux on both boundaries (mimicking fixed-flux thermal convection). Simulation runtimes vary from 0.01-33.48 magnetic diffusion times.

A variety of output diagnostics for the simulations are reported in Supplementary Table 1 for completeness and all values of the global diagnostics of the geodynamo simulation are given as the spatio-temporal mean. Here we are mainly interested in the following outputs: the magnetic Reynolds number $Rm = UD/\eta$, measuring the ratio of magnetic induction and diffusion; the Elsasser number $\Lambda = \sigma B^2/(\rho\Omega)$, a measure of the strength of Lorentz to Coriolis forces; the magnetic to kinetic energy ratio $E_m/E_k = \Lambda Pm/(Rm^2 E)$; and the dipolarity f_d^L of the field at the top of the core. Here U and B are respectively the RMS fluid velocity and magnetic field strength, ρ is the fluid density, and σ the electrical conductivity. The power R_l in the magnetic field for spherical harmonic degree l (Loves, 1966) can be evaluated by

$$R_l(r) = \sum_{m=0}^l R_{l,m}, \quad (1)$$

$$R_{l,m}(r) = \left(\frac{r_e}{r}\right)^{2l+4} (l+1) [(g_{l,m})^2 + (h_{l,m})^2], \quad (2)$$

where $g_{l,m}$ and $h_{l,m}$ are Schmidt-normalised Gauss coefficients of degree l and order m evaluated at Earth's radius r_e . The dipolarity at the CMB radius r_c is given by

$$f_d^L = \sqrt{\frac{R_1(r_c)}{\sum_{l=1}^L R_l(r_c)}}. \quad (3)$$

and is often calculated using spherical harmonic coefficients up to degree $L = 12$, with $f_d^{12} = 0.35$ used as a proxy for the dipole-multipole transition (Christensen and Aubert, 2006). Hereafter, we denote f_d to be the standard $L = 12$ definition (f_d^{12}) adopted in the dynamo modelling community. Degree $L = 12$ marks the transition between crustal- and core-dominated magnetic field spectra in the modern field and therefore represents the maximum resolvable degree under ideal temporal and spatial coverage. We will also report f_d^4 for comparison to geomagnetic field models spanning Holocene and longer timescales which only recover large-scale features of the field.

Figure 1 illustrates the parameter space sampled by our simulations. The values of E and Pm are, like all direct numerical simulations of the geodynamo, orders of magnitude higher than the values $E \sim 10^{-15}$ and $Pm \sim 10^{-6}$ that characterise Earth's core (Davies et al., 2015). Nevertheless, these parameters are densely sampled over two orders of magnitude and output diagnostics Λ and Rm (which are time averages of RMS values across the simulations) span ranges appropriate for the geodynamo. The simulations also span a wide range of field morphologies at the top of the core, from multipolar solutions that generally have average $E_m/E_k < 1$, to dipole-dominated non-reversing behaviour that often arise when $E_m/E_k \gg 1$. Simulations with $E_m/E_k < 1$ are shown in grey to indicate that they are unlikely to be in the expected 'strong-field' regime (Nakagawa and Davies, 2022). 67 simulations exhibit a reversal during their run. Sampling

Figure 1: Summary of characteristics of the dynamos considered in this study: (a) Ekman number (ratio of viscous forces to Coriolis forces) against magnetic Prandtl number (ratio of viscous diffusivity to magnetic diffusivity). (b) magnetic Reynolds number (magnetic advection to magnetic diffusion) against the Elsasser number (ratio of Lorentz force to Coriolis force). The size of the points are proportional to the magnetic Reynolds number and the colour indicates the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. Simulations coloured grey reflect those having a mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio less than 1, unlikely to be in the strong-field regime. Indicative Earth values are shown in blue. Three simulations (LEDCJ001, LEDT010_SM, and LEDTF001) are marked for comparison in relation to later figures in this manuscript.

this broad range of dynamo and field behaviour is important for testing simulations against a range of geomagnetic observations.

3 Overview of criteria

We consider the metrics in Table 1, which have been used in previous studies to quantify agreement between geodynamo simulation outputs and observations. They cover a wide range of timescales spanning the historical field (< 400 years) which exhibits limited secular variation, to large changes such as geomagnetic excursions and polarity reversals, which take 10s of ky to complete and occur a few times per My, and are based on various statistics representing average morphology and variability of the field. Several have been combined (as in, for example, Christensen et al., 2010; Sprain et al., 2019) to produce a χ^2 or other misfit score as a measure of compliance between a simulation and the geomagnetic field. Here we instead choose to consider each metric individually rather than mixing potentially disparate measures of morphology and variability. Unlike geodynamo diagnostics, observational quantities (and the criteria built from these) are skewed by the uneven distribution in time and space and, therefore, paleomagnetic studies often report the median or remove outliers to account for this.

The first step for calculating each criterion is to truncate the geomagnetic field output from the numerical dynamo simulation to a maximum spherical harmonic degree for fair comparison to the observations. Recent work (as in, for example, Panovska et al., 2019; Wardinski et al., 2025) has shown that changing the maximum spherical harmonic degree of criteria can affect the resulting values calculated from the Gauss coefficients. In this work we only consider the spherical harmonic degree truncation and observational bounds given in the original study, summarised in Table 1.

3.1 Morphological compliance criteria

Christensen et al. (2010) defined 4 criteria that quantify similarities between simulated and observed magnetic field mor-

phologies based on spherical harmonic series truncated at degree $L = 8$. A_N is the ratio of axial dipole power to the non-axial dipole power in the Lowes spectrum:

$$A_N = \frac{R_{1,0}(r_c)}{R_{1,1}(r_c) + \sum_{l=2}^L R_l(r_c)}. \quad (4)$$

Equatorial asymmetry in the non-dipole field, O_E , is calculated from the ratio of power in spherical harmonic terms with $(l + m)$ odd over even. Z_N relates power in zonal ($m = 0$) to non-zonal ($m \neq 0$) terms bringing in a measure of longitudinal variability. The flux concentration factor (F_C) is a measure of the relative spatial concentration of magnetic flux specified by the spatial average (here represented by angle brackets) of the squared radial field:

$$F_C = \left[\langle B_r^4 \rangle - \langle B_r^2 \rangle^2 \right] / \langle B_r^2 \rangle^2. \quad (5)$$

Christensen et al. (2010) calculate a χ^2 misfit between simulated and observed values for each criterion $C_i \in \{A_N, O_E, Z_N, F_C\}$ as

$$\chi_i^2 = \left[\left(\ln(C_i) - \ln(C_i^E) \right) / \ln(\sigma_{C_i}^E) \right]^2, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma_{C_i}^E$ is the multiplicative factor assigned to be the bounds of the observed values C_i^E . Each criterion can be considered individually (χ_i^2) or all 4 can be summed to provide a total compliance rating (χ^2). Christensen et al. (2010) define $\chi^2 > 8$ as ‘non-compliant’, $\chi^2 < 4$ as ‘good’ compliance, and $\chi^2 < 2$ as ‘excellent’ compliance to Earth. (Note that for a χ^2 distribution with n degrees of freedom we expect the average to be $\bar{\chi}^2 = n$, and the $\sigma_{\chi^2} = \sqrt{2n}$, with one-sided 90th and 95th percentile for χ_4^2 with $n=4$ as ≈ 7.8 and ≈ 9.5 .)

We take the values of C_i^E and $\sigma_{C_i}^E$ used by Christensen et al. (2010) (Table 1), which are largely based on the historical field model *gufm1* with allowance in $\sigma_{C_i}^E$ for additional variability in the paleofield. Recently, Wardinski et al. (2025) have calculated C_i values for a range of field models spanning the period 3–100 ka (see also Panovska et al., 2019). Compared to Table 1, they find comparable values of O_E and Z_N , but higher values of A_N (by a factor of 2–5) and lower

Table 1: Summary of all metrics considered in this study including a short description, symbol(s), the proposed range of values, and the reference for where the range is described. We define the observationally-constrained range as median^{+upper bound difference}_{-lower bound difference}. Some Q_{PM} components are rounded. Generally, these reflect 95% of the distribution based on the models or observations used in their constructions (see original papers for full details).

Name of Criterion	Description	Symbol	Earth-like range	Reference
Morphological compliance criteria	Summary metric χ^2 comprised of four measures of field morphology: axial dipole dominance A_N , zonality Z_N , equatorial antisymmetry O_E , and flux concentration F_C	χ^2 A_N O_E Z_N F_C	0-8 $1.4^{+1.4}_{-0.7}$ $1.0^{+1.0}_{-0.5}$ $0.15^{+0.23}_{-0.09}$ $1.50^{+1.13}_{-0.64}$	Christensen et al. (2010)
Hemispherical balance of flux	Measure of west-east hemispherical total flux (F) and flux concentration factor (F_C , from above) in 4 high-latitude quadrants	H_{F^*} $H_{F_C^*}$	$0.03^{+0.14}_{-0.16}$ $0.03^{+0.13}_{-0.16}$	Mound et al. (2015)
SV timescale	Fit to non-dipole low degree ratio of field spectra and secular variation	τ_{SV}	415^{+55}_{-45} yrs	Lhuillier et al. (2011)
Paleosecular Variation Index	Normalised ratio of angular deviation of VGP from the spin axis to the virtual dipole moment	P_1 P_1^{max} P_1	$0.10^{+0.10}_{-0.02}$ > 0.5	Panovska et al. (2019) Mason et al. (2024)
Quality of Paleomagnetic Modelling Criteria	Summary metric ΔQ_{PM} comprising four measures (assessed from downsampled simulations at the locations of PSV10, Cromwell et al., 2018): maximum inclination anomaly ΔI^{max} , a and b parameters characterising VGP dispersion, VDM variability V_f , and proportion of time spent in transitional periods τ_t	ΔQ_{PM} ΔI^{max} a b V_f τ_t	0-5 7.04° ^{+1.35°} _{-1.40°} 11.33° ^{+1.93°} _{-1.64°} $0.26^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$ $0.70^{+0.17}_{-0.17}$ $0.09^{+0.06}_{-0.06}$	Sprain et al. (2019) Bono (pers. comm., 2025)

values of F_C (by a factor of 1.5). These differences reflect some combination of different geomagnetic field behaviour (e.g. paleosecular variation, presence of excursions), different modelling strategies, and the loss of resolution at higher l with varying spatio-temporal data distributions.

3.2 Hemispheric balance of flux ($H_{F_C^*}$, H_{F^*})

Mound et al. (2015) considered regional variations in four high latitude quadrants Q defined from 0° and 180° lines of longitude, and each pole (0° or 180°) and the 30° lines of latitude (60° or 120° colatitude). For each quadrant, the flux concentration factor (F_C) and the total integrated flux (F) are calculated up to $L = 8$ by:

$$F_{CQ} = \frac{\langle B_r(Q)^4 \rangle - \langle B_r(Q)^2 \rangle^2}{\langle B_r(Q)^2 \rangle^2}, \quad (7)$$

$$F_Q = \int \int_\theta^\phi B_r dQ. \quad (8)$$

These are normalised by the values obtained by considering only the axial dipole component of the field. Finally the hemispheric difference in high-latitude flux concentration can be calculated by considering the normalised values (F_C^* , F^*) in each quadrant (Q^* , NorthWest, SouthWest, NorthEast, SouthEast) by:

$$H_{F_C^*}, H_{F^*} = \frac{(Q_{NW}^* + Q_{SW}^*) - (Q_{NE}^* + Q_{SE}^*)}{(Q_{NW}^* + Q_{SW}^*) + (Q_{NE}^* + Q_{SE}^*)}. \quad (9)$$

$H_{F_C^*}$ and H_{F^*} are usually bounded between ± 1 , with a value of 0 indicating that the east and west quadrants have equal flux, except at times when one of the quadrant values are negative. This happens when the coefficients for spherical harmonic degrees greater than one are larger and of the opposite sign

to the dipole, a sign of intense reverse flux patches. We therefore calculate H_{F^*} only at times where all quadrant values are positive and state a $H_{F\%}$ which is the proportion of the simulation where no quadrants are negative.

In Table 1 we use the observationally-constrained ranges of $H_{F_C^*}$ and H_{F^*} for the *gufm1* and *CALS10k.1* field models, taken from Mound et al. (2015). The values are very similar despite the different resolutions and timespans of the individual field models.

3.3 Secular variation timescale (τ_{SV})

The secular variation timescale is based on a parametric fit of the ratio of the spatial power spectra of the field to its secular variation as a function of l (Christensen and Tilgner, 2004; Lhuillier et al., 2011):

$$\tau_l = \sqrt{\frac{R_l}{S_l}}, \quad (10)$$

where S_l is the secular variation power equivalent of equation (2) defined using the secular variation coefficients \dot{g}_{lm} and \dot{h}_{lm} . Using spherical harmonic degrees 2–12, τ_l falls off as $\sim 1/l$ for the modern field leading to a definition of an overall secular variation timescale

$$\tau_{SV} = l \tau_l. \quad (11)$$

The observed value of τ_{SV} depends somewhat on the field model and timespan considered, with the instantaneous values since 2000 spanning the approximate range $350 \leq \tau_{SV} \leq 490$ (Christensen et al., 2012; Amit et al., 2018). Here we use the bounds suggested by Lhuillier et al. (2011): $\tau_{SV} = 415^{+55}_{-45}$.

3.4 Paleosecular variation index (P_1)

Both excursions and reversals are known properties of the geomagnetic field. The paleosecular variation index $P_1(t, \lambda, \phi)$

is a combined measure of magnetic field strength and direction designed to identify when the geomagnetic field is in an excursions state that may or may not lead to reversal. It is large when the virtual dipole moment, V , is low and the VGP lies far from the geographic axis. Panovska and Constable (2017) specify $P_1(t) > 0.5$ to characterise the start of a geomagnetic excursion, and Constable and Morzfeld (2024) extended its use to evaluate the time spent in an excursion or reversal event specifying the end time as the first return to below the average value.

$P_1(t, \lambda, \phi)$ can be measured locally or globally and local events might not register in the global measure. Here we focus on the spatial mean of $P_1(t, \lambda, \phi)$, which is computed from the local magnetic field vector based on Gauss coefficients up to $L = 5$, translated to VGP latitude λ_V and V before being averaged globally, following Mason et al. (2024):

$$P_1(t) = \left\langle \frac{(\pi/2 - |\lambda_V(t)|) V_0}{\pi V(t)} \right\rangle, \quad (12)$$

where V_0 is an estimate of the average of V over space and time. Mason et al. (2024) used GGF100k to obtain an observed global average range $0.08 < \text{mean}(P_1(t)) < 0.20$. Despite the temporal smoothness of the GGF100k model, we utilise this range to be our observational bounds for the median($P_1(t)$) (hereafter P_1) since it is currently the only spherical harmonic field representation spanning the last 100 kyrs. However, matching P_1 does not guarantee that a simulation produces excursions or reversals. For this we require that simulations produce $P_1^{max} > 0.5$, where P_1^{max} denotes the maximum value of the time-series of $P_1(t)$.

3.5 Quality of Paleomagnetic Modelling criteria (Q_{PM})

Sprain et al. (2019) define five disparate measures of similarities between simulated fields, truncated at $L = 10$, and paleomagnetic observations spanning the past ~ 10 Myrs. The criterion ΔI^{max} , measures the temporal median of the maximum deviation of the inclination (calculated from 10° latitude bins and provided with 95% confidence intervals) from that produced by a GAD field. Two criteria measuring directional variability over time are derived from geographic variability in the dispersion S of VGP directions,

$$S(\lambda) = \left[\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta_i^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (13)$$

where Δ_i is the angular distance of the i^{th} VGP from the geographic pole. The latitudinal variation of S is frequently approximated by a parametric fit known as Model G (McFadden et al., 1988; Biggin et al., 2008), given by

$$S^2(\lambda) = a^2 + (b \lambda)^2, \quad (14)$$

where a and b represent, respectively, the VGP scatter at the equator and its increase with latitude λ . a and b are obtained from a least squares fit to time-averaged dispersion, S , over specified latitude bins and provide two contributions to the overall Q_{PM} score. The fourth criterion, V_f , is a measure of variability in global field strength and uses q^V , the interquartile range of virtual dipole moment V , normalised by its median value \widehat{V}

$$V_f = \frac{q^V}{\widehat{V}}. \quad (15)$$

The fifth and final criterion, τ_t , quantifies the proportion of total time the field spends in transition between polarities. We define times with normal polarity where dipole latitude $> 45^\circ$, τ_n , time with reverse polarity where dipole latitude $< 45^\circ$, τ_r , and the transitional time as the period when dipole latitude lies between 45° and -45° , τ_t . A simulation matches this criterion if $\tau_n, \tau_r > \tau_t$ and τ_t falls within the range estimated for Earth.

Values for each of the Q_{PM} criteria expected for Earth are written as C_m^E and we use updated values obtained from PSV10 (Bono, pers. comm, 2025) and given in Table 1. The misfit between simulated and observed values for each criterion C_m is calculated via

$$\Delta Q_{PM}^i = \frac{|C_m^E - C_m|}{C_m^E + C_{\sigma_m}} \quad m=1, \dots, 5, \quad (16)$$

where C_{σ_m} denote the 95% confidence bounds and superscript E denotes Earth-values. The individual measures for ΔQ_{PM}^i can be summed to provide a composite measure (ΔQ_{PM}), but this is less useful than considering the individual evaluations because it assigns equal weight to the misfit of each component. A simulation is considered 'Earth-like' when $\Delta Q_{PM} < 5$, but it may not necessarily pass every component Sprain et al. (2019).

3.6 Application of criteria

The selection of criteria and typical values outlined above draws heavily on what is available in the form of observations, and there are obviously fundamental limitations in what we know. In paleomagnetic data compilations (such as PSV10, Cromwell et al., 2018; PSV10-24, Tauxe et al., 2024 that nominally span the past 10 My) the observations based on lava flows are unevenly distributed in space and time. The evaluation of S typically excludes transitional data so we should not expect a and b to be compatible with measures like P_1 or V_f . P_1 relies on both field strength and direction to identify transitional field behaviour, but τ_t only uses directions which are more numerous than full vector data. ΔI^{max} is the main measure of long-timescale field morphology, which relies on having a good estimate of the temporal and spatial coverage for the field. Criteria based on spherical harmonic representations (e.g. f_d , C_i , τ_{SV}) will inevitably vary with time due to both intrinsic field variations and changes in the resolution that is afforded by available observations. We use estimates of these quantities based on high-resolution models of the modern geomagnetic field, but note that these values might not be representative of longer timescales.

Geodynamo simulations output the magnetic field throughout the shell, which can be used to derive all of the above statistics at variable resolution up to and exceeding that afforded by observations. However, simulations should be run long enough to ensure a stable measure of the time-averaged field, which could be a few kyrs for the non-dipole field but is much longer for the axial dipole (Davies and Constable, 2014). The simulations in this study span 0.01-33.48 magnetic diffusion times, which represent 1,500-6,696,000 years when rescaled to dimensional units using the magnetic diffusion time $D^2/\eta \approx 150 - 200$ kyrs using an electrical conductivity of $0.75 - 1 \times 10^6$ S m^{-1} (Pozzo et al., 2022). 46 of our simulations span less than 0.5

Figure 2: Probability density function of f_d for the three example simulations shown in Figures 1 and 3. The f_d in 2025.0 and the bounds for f_d suggested by Davies et al. (2022) are shown for reference.

diffusion times ($\sim 1.5 - 100$ kyrs) but most are long enough to provide robust estimates for all criteria in the upper section of Table 1. The Q_{PM} criteria are constrained from PSV10, which is dominated by data from the last 2 Myrs. Only 62 of our simulations span the equivalent of > 1 Myrs, but we nevertheless compute the Q_{PM} criteria for all simulations. We might expect that short duration runs underestimate the Q_{PM} score by virtue of not being long enough to sample infrequent events like reversals and excursions, or the general level of long-term variability. The fact that our simulations are generally longer than the historical record (400 yrs) presents some ambiguity for comparing against the criteria C_i and τ_{SV} that are based on short-term field observations. Here we use both the temporal average and minimum value across the simulations for these comparisons. The first comparison effectively assumes that values for these criteria obtained from the modern geomagnetic field are reflective of longer term averages. The second comparison assumes that the modern field is effectively an instantaneous realisation of field behaviour that should be matched at least once by a given simulation.

4 Simulation-observation comparisons using individual criteria

Figure 2 shows the probability density function of f_d over time for three example simulations (LEDCJ001, LEDTF001 and LEDT010_SM). These simulations all produce a strong magnetic field with $E_m/E_k > 1$ and $Rm > 500$, which is compatible with inferences on core material properties and surface flow speeds. LEDCJ001 produces a dipolarity comparable to the modern geomagnetic field while LEDTF001 and LEDT010_SM have a lower f_d . All three simulations produce asymmetric distributions, particularly LEDTF001, which has a long tail at low f_d arising from excursions and reversals when the dipole field significantly weakens. Similar results are obtained for other quantities that are influenced by long timescale variations, such as A_N and P_1 . In symmetric distributions, the mean, median, and peak of distribution tend to coincide, whereas greater asymmetry or the presence of extreme values causes the mean to diverge from the other mea-

asures. Therefore, to ensure robust statistics, throughout this work we use the median and interquartile range when characterising the temporal average and variance of individual criteria or quantities derived from Gauss coefficients (such as f_d). Similar to P_1 , median(f_d) will hereafter be simplified to f_d .

Figure 3 shows a selection of criteria evaluated from the three example simulations in Figure 2 to demonstrate their application. LEDCJ001 has a relatively stable field at the top of the core that is morphologically similar to the modern field over most of its evolution, but does not produce excursions or reversals and is not sufficiently variable to match observed values for P_1 and some of the Q_{PM} criteria. LEDT010_SM produces a field at the outer boundary that is occasionally compliant with the modern geomagnetic field morphology, but does provide a good match to P_1 from GGF100k, the Q_{PM} VGP dispersion, and ΔI^{max} . LEDTF001 produces behaviour that is intermediate between the two previous simulations, despite having a similar f_d to LEDT010_SM. LEDTF001 has higher f_d variability (shown in Figure 2) and produces sustained periods of good morphological compliance with the modern geomagnetic field, a median P_1 that is consistent with GGF100k and a plausible VGP dispersion and ΔI^{max} values. The high variability of A_N and $P_1(t)$ in LEDTF001 causes the mean and median values to differ significantly (mean($\chi^2(t)$) = 9.98, median($\chi^2(t)$) = 5.48, mean($P_1(t)$) = 0.194, $P_1 = 0.104$).

In the remainder of this section we assess our simulation dataset in terms of individual criteria, before performing cross-comparisons in Section 5. We split criteria into those that assess field morphology (compliance criteria C_i , H_{FC} , H_F , ΔI^{max}) and those that assess variability (τ_{SV} , P_1 , a , b , V_f and τ_t). This distinction is somewhat artificial given that the variance of any quantity could in principle be used to assess temporal variability, and rather reflects the original context in which the criteria were defined and helps to simplify the presentation. We focus on the variation of criteria with f_d , Rm and E_m/E_k based on results obtained by previous studies (Christensen et al., 2010; Christensen et al., 2012; Meduri et al., 2021; Tassin et al., 2021; Nakagawa and Davies, 2022).

Figure 3: Example dynamo input and output diagnostics, and metric outputs for three dynamo simulations shown in bold in Figure 1. The first row shows a snapshot normalised to the maximum B_r value at the upper boundary of that snapshot for the timestep where Rm and f_{dip} are closest to their average values. The second row shows the stacked $\chi^2(t)$ values against time from the morphological compliance criteria. The median χ^2 value is marked as a grey dashed line. The third row shows the Paleosecular Variation Index ($P_i(t)$) against time with the median marked as a red dashed line. The grey vertical bar marks the location of the snapshot shown in the first row. Earth-like values of P_i are given in grey and excursion and reversal behaviour is shown in blue. The final row is VGP dispersion (pink, used to construct model G (McFadden et al., 1988; Biggin et al., 2019)) and the maximum deviation of the inclination (green) for the dynamo simulations both plotted as a function of latitude. We remind the reader that global diagnostics of the geodynamo simulation are given as the spatio-temporal mean and the observable quantities or metrics derived from Gauss coefficients are reported using the spatial mean and temporal median.

Figure 4: The individual components of the compliance criteria computed for all dynamos: (a) A_N , (b) O_E , (c) Z_N , and (d) F_C . The observationally-constrained mean value for the compliance values and its bounds (shown as a blue horizontal line and shaded region) to calculate χ^2 are given in Table 1. The size of the points are proportional to magnetic Reynolds number, the CMB boundary conditions are shown by symbol, and the colour bar is the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. $\chi^2 < 8$ can be found between $0.46 < f_d < 0.80$ and $\min(\chi^2(t)) < 8$ can be found between $0.15 < f_d < 0.94$. The reference simulations from Figure 3 are marked for comparison.

4.1 Criteria based on field morphology

Figure 4 shows A_N , Z_N , O_E and F_C as a function of f_d , E_m/E_k and Rm . We find an expected correlation between A_N and f_d , which both measure dipolarity but in different ways. The vast majority of our simulations pass Z_N and O_E (lie within the blue band) regardless of the value of f_d and E_m/E_k . Simulations that do not meet these criteria generally have Rm either too small or too large compared to Earth's core, though a wide range of Rm values are acceptable. For F_C , simulations exist that comply with the criterion across the whole range of f_d , but most produce values that are higher than the observational range proposed by Christensen et al. (2010) for $f_d < 0.7$. These trends are independent of the outer thermal boundary conditions. Overall, 59 simulations are considered 'compliant' with the modern geomagnetic field based on the criterion $\chi^2 < 8$. These simulations have $0.46 < f_d < 0.80$, $105 < Rm < 1761$, $0.1 < E_m/E_k < 22.9$. However, as discussed in Section 3.6, given that the length of the simulations far exceeds that of the historical record, it is perhaps more appropriate to consider $\min(\chi^2(t))$ across time. In this case, 126 more dynamos fall within the 'compliant' category which have $0.15 < f_d < 0.94$, $72 < Rm < 12073$, and $0.007 < E_m/E_k < 64.0$.

Figure 5 shows that both $H_{F_C}^*$ and H_{F^*} for all simulations cluster close to 0 and almost all lie within the range extracted from field models, indicating no time-averaged east-west preference for integrated flux or patchiness. This is to be expected since the $H_{F_C}^*$ and H_{F^*} criteria were designed

to distinguish simulations with variable hemispheric forcing on the inner boundary (Mound et al., 2015), which is absent in our dataset. Nevertheless, even our simulations with tomographic (Y_2^2 -dominated) CMB forcing cannot be discriminated from homogeneous simulations using the $H_{F_C}^*$ and H_{F^*} criteria despite these heterogeneous simulations sometimes producing persistent hemispherically variable outputs (Aubert et al., 2008). Panel (b) shows that dynamos with low H_{F^*} (shown by increasing transparency) tend to lie below the dipole-multipole transition ($f_d = 0.35$).

Figure 6 shows that ΔI^{max} tends to vary inversely with f_d as found by Meduri et al. (2021). As with the morphological compliance criteria, the different boundary conditions do not impact the trend. The range of f_d where simulations match the ΔI^{max} given for Earth is 0.4–0.8 but with the majority of simulations having f_d lying between 0.4 and 0.6. Simulations that satisfy the ΔI^{max} range tend to have $E_m/E_k > 1$ and a moderate Rm , though simulations from across the full range of properties ($0.1 < E_m/E_k < 64.0$, $88 < Rm < 2148$) can satisfy the criterion.

4.2 Criteria based on variability

Figure 7 shows τ_{SV} vs. Rm for our simulation dataset. The relation $\tau_{SV} \propto Rm^{-1}$, suggested by Christensen and Tilgner (2004), does an excellent job of fitting the whole dataset (correlation is -0.97), with perhaps slightly more variation at low Rm . There is no significant dependence of τ_{SV} on boundary conditions, E_m/E_k (correlation is -0.16) or f_d (correla-

Figure 5: Hemispherical flux concentration for all dynamos: (a) f_d against $H_{F_C}^*$, (b) f_d against H_{F^*} , (c) H_{F^*} against $H_{F_C}^*$. The greater the transparency of the fill of H_{F^*} markers, the lower the $H_{F\%}$. Almost all simulations lie within the observationally-constrained limits, shown in blue, given in Table 1, meaning that it cannot be used to distinguish ‘Earth-like’ behaviour or those with heterogeneous forcing. The size of the points are proportional to magnetic Reynolds number, the CMB boundary conditions are shown by symbol, and the colour bar is the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. The reference simulations from Figure 3 are marked for comparison.

tion is 0.21), and simulations matching τ_{SV} cover almost the full parameter space of our dataset ($0.48 < E_m/E_k < 15.8$, $0.27 < f_d < 0.68$). Based on the τ_{SV} values estimated by Lhuillier et al. (2011), simulations with $789 < Rm < 1196$ match the criterion. Unlike the compliance criteria, the value of τ_{SV} is quite stable over the timespans of simulations regardless of whether we consider mean or median, or consider the average of τ_{SV} at each timestep or the average of the spectra. Rm (and consequently τ_{SV}) varies by around 10% during the run regardless of duration, therefore τ_{SV}^{\min} continues to follow the $1/Rm$ relationship but is offset with a lower intercept and the range of plausible Rm is extended to $386 < Rm < 1214$.

Figure 8 displays properties of the PSV index for our dataset. The quasi-linear variation of P_1 with f_d is striking, with simulations in the range $f_d = 0.29 - 0.64$ consistent with constraints from GGF100k. P_1^{\max} also varies strongly with f_d and values of $f_d \lesssim 0.4$ show a noticeable increase in

P_1^{\max} as simulations are often in the weak field regime with some being multipolar. The 101 simulations that are consistent with P_1^{\max} from GGF100k have $f_d < 0.59$ and simulations that are consistent with both P_1 and P_1^{\max} lie in the range $0.29 < f_d < 0.47$. There is no clear variation of P_1 with Rm or E_m/E_k , agreeing with the findings of Mason et al. (2024) who used a much smaller dataset. The duration of the simulation does not appear to significantly affect the median P_1 , while simulations with a duration of less than 0.5 magnetic diffusion times (approximately 75 kyr) generally have the lowest P_1^{\max} values, perhaps as they have not been run for long enough to sample infrequent but large values of P_1 .

Figure 9 shows the behaviour of the 4 Q_{PM} criteria that relate to field variability. Figure 9(a) verifies the inverse relation between f_d and a with a range of Earth-like f_d values between 0.43 and 0.61, and no clear trend with E_m/E_k or Rm . b (Figure 9(b)) requires a wider range of f_d (0.13-0.64)

Figure 6: Temporal median of the maximum inclination anomaly against f_d . The observationally-constrained median and 95% confidence, shown in blue, are given in Table 1. The size of the points are proportional to magnetic Reynolds number, the CMB boundary conditions are shown by symbol, and the colour bar is the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. The reference simulations from Figure 3 are marked for comparison.

Figure 7: Rm against the SV timescale (τ_{SV}). The $1/Rm$ relationship is shown by a dashed line. The bounds derived from observations, shown in blue, are given in Table 1. The size of the points are proportional to magnetic Reynolds number, the CMB boundary conditions are shown by symbol, and the colour bar is the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. The reference simulations from Figure 3 are marked for comparison.

Figure 8: f_d against P_i (a) and P_i^{max} (b). The field-model-derived values (blue shading) are given in Table 1. The size of the points are proportional to magnetic Reynolds number, and the filled symbols indicate whether the simulation is shorter (diamond) or longer (pentagon) than 0.5 magnetic diffusion times (~ 75 kyr). The colour bar is the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. The reference simulations from Figure 3 are marked for comparison.

Figure 9: The Q_{PM} criteria variability components computed for all dynamo as a function of f_d : (a) a , (b) b , (c) V_f , and (d) the proportion of the simulation in transitional state. The median and 95% bounds are given in Table 1 and shown in blue. The size of the points are proportional to magnetic Reynolds number, and the filled symbols indicate whether the simulation is shorter (diamond) or longer (pentagon) than 3 magnetic diffusion times (same cut-off as Sprain et al. (2019)). The colour bar is the mean magnetic to kinetic energy ratio. The reference simulations from Figure 3 are marked for comparison.

but within this range there is significant variability and no trend with f_d , E_m/E_k or Rm . Figure 9(c) shows that V_f follows a similar trend to a , but with the compliant range of f_d lowered to f_d between 0.11 and 0.57. Finally, the transitional time has a very rapid decrease between $f_d = 0 - 0.35$, reflecting the dipole-multipole transition around 0.35 (Christensen and Aubert, 2006). Simulations with $f_d > 0.35$ are close to $\tau_t = 0$ and Earth-like values of the transitional time requires $0.29 < f_d < 0.47$. As shown by Meduri et al. (2021) and clarified here, matching the Q_{PM} criteria within the avail-

able dataset is a balance between the components requiring lower f_d (V_f , τ_t) and those that are most readily satisfied with higher f_d (a , ΔI^{max}). Simulations are only compatible with all Q_{PM} criteria within a narrow f_d window (0.37 – 0.59), mostly because the maximum f_d for the fractional transitional time criterion is much lower than other criteria, reflecting the lack of reversing dynamo with a large time-averaged dipolarity. Although only 62 of our simulations were run for longer than the ideal 1 Myr timescale, 103 are run for longer than 3 magnetic diffusion times. Regardless of the duration, the trends

are consistent for all criteria for simulations. Once again, the CMB boundary conditions produce no distinguishable differences.

Biggin et al. (2020) found an inverse relationship between a and median axial dominance at Earth's surface. We extend this result to a relationship between a and f_d using the relationship $\log(a) = -3.56f_d + 4.38$, marked on Figure 9(a). Using the a estimates over 0-2.9 Ga from Biggin et al. (2020), we estimate f_d over these periods to lie between 0.48 and 0.64. This range of f_d is somewhat lower than Earth's modern field, which has a higher dipolarity of $f_d \sim 0.71$ (calculated from CHAOS-8.1, Kloss et al., 2026). This range is slightly extended when we exclude multipolar dynamos ($f_d < 0.35$) and strongly dipolar dynamos ($f_d > 0.75$) when deriving the a - f_d relationship. In this case, the dipolarity inferred from the ranges of a given by Biggin et al. (2020) is between 0.46 and 0.66.

5 Simulation-observation comparisons using multiple criteria

We now consider the characteristics of simulations that enable multiple criteria to be matched simultaneously. To do this we must identify a low-dimensional parameter space that adequately captures the behaviour of simulations with a vast range of control parameters (E , Pm , Ra , etc) and output diagnostics (Rm , E_m/E_k , etc). Christensen et al. (2010) found that low χ^2 scores tended to arise in a particular area of $Rm - E/Pm$ parameter space, but other studies have found high χ^2 (Davies and Constable, 2014; Tassin et al., 2021) and Q_{PM} (Sprain et al., 2019) misfits in this parameter region. We find (Figure A.1 in Appendix A) that dynamos within the wedge are more likely to match the existing criteria, but can also perform poorly against many of the 14 metrics. Nakagawa and Davies (2022) showed that simulations with a $E_m/E_k > 1$ and moderate $0.35 < f_d < 0.75$ tend to lie in the strong-field regime and have better $\min(\chi^2(t))$ compliance. We find (Figure A.2 in Appendix A) that simulations with $E_m/E_k > 1$ and $0.35 < f_d < 0.75$ are also more likely to match the compliance and other criteria but can also perform poorly. Mason et al. (2024) found no significant correlation between either mean($P_1(t)$) or P_1^{max} and a number of global dynamo parameters including Λ , E/Pm and E_m/E_k . Here we choose to use f_d (median(f_d)) and normalised variability of f_d , where the interquartile range is divided by the median ($\delta f_d = q_{f_d}/f_d$). Although these quantities are output diagnostics from dynamo simulations, they have the advantage of directly measuring morphology and variability of the CMB field. They can also be calculated from global observational field models, and have been used previously to diagnose the dipole-multipole transition (Frasson et al., 2025; Burmann et al., 2025).

Hereafter we focus on a subset of the criteria considered in Section 4. The SV timescale essentially requires $750 \leq Rm \leq 1200$ (see Figure 7) and so we account for this by highlighting simulations in this range. The criteria H_{FC} , H_F , Z_N and O_E are passed by the majority of our simulations, meaning they do not have significant discriminatory power as noted by Jones and Tsang (2025), and the simulations that do not pass generally have Rm outside the range required by τ_{SV} . This may be because the assigned bounds on these quantities are not well characterised. We further discount F_C be-

cause it depends sensitively on spatio-temporal resolution and methodology of the field model from which it is derived, and b because it is sensitive to data selection and the handling of transitional directions. Since simulations across the full range of E_m/E_k , Rm and f_d in our dataset pass F_C , and given that b does not provide additional constraints beyond other Q_{PM} criteria (specifically V_f and a), these omissions do not change our conclusions.

In Figure 10 we show the misfit of A_N , ΔI^{max} , P_1 , a , V_f and τ_t for ranges of f_d and normalised variability (δf_d). We draw bounding polygons (or 'convex hulls') containing all simulations that match each criterion. Owing to the limited number of simulations these polygons probably underestimate the region of $f_d - \delta f_d$ space where each criterion is met, and also contain simulations that do not meet the criterion. Nevertheless, they provide a simple representation that allows us to visualise how simulations satisfy multiple criteria. Two key points emerge from Figure 10. First, all simulations plot along a general trend where δf_d is inversely correlated with f_d (see also Burmann et al., 2025). The relative variability decreases sharply at the dipolar-multipolar transition around $f_d \sim 0.35$ (Tassin et al., 2021). We note that this trend is reminiscent of findings from palaeomagnetic studies that link higher reversals rates to lower average dipole strength (Valet et al., 2005). Second, simulations with larger f_d have a low δf_d and better match morphological criteria such as A_N and ΔI^{max} . Conversely, simulations with lower f_d and larger δf_d better match variability criteria such as V_f and τ_t . Indeed, even within the Q_{PM} criteria, which all explore the same timescale, τ_t has an incompatible range of δf_d and f_d compared to ΔI^{max} and a . A similar figure but with f_d and δf_d truncated at $L = 4$ is shown in Figure A.3 in Appendix A to enable comparison with lower resolution global paleofield models.

In Figure 11(a) we combine the polygons of Figure 10 (also adding results for P_1^{max}). The greatest overlap among polygons lies near the lower estimate of f_d inferred from a . There is no overlap across all polygons, which is primarily due to the distinct ranges of f_d and δf_d spanned by median A_N and τ_t . This difference is significantly diminished if we consider instantaneous A_N , in which case the polygons of A_N , ΔI , a and τ_t almost overlap. Given the uncertainty in the precise boundaries of the individual polygons, we would therefore expect that all criteria would overlap around $f_d \sim 0.4 - 0.5$ and $\delta f_d \sim 0.1 - 0.2$, similar to the lower value of f_d inferred from a . In our dataset the largest number of criteria that any of the simulations match is 6 (out of 8, shown by the 7 polygons together with $360 < \tau_{SV} < 470$), which is achieved by a single simulation with $f_d = 0.38$ and $\delta f_d = 0.226$. At the f_d value of modern Earth our simulations match morphological properties of the geomagnetic field, but not its long-term variability. There is a broad separation between reversing simulations, which can match V_f , τ_t , P_1 and P_1^{max} , but not a , A_N and ΔI , and non-reversing simulations that generally do not match V_f and τ_t . All 67 reversing simulations lie within the P_1^{max} polygon together with an additional 34 simulations exhibiting excursions. Simulations with Rm within and outside the range $750 < Rm < 1200$ are found in every polygon, suggesting that Rm does not control the compliance to the criteria used to define these polygons. Similarly, the magnetic to kinetic energy ratio does not determine on its own

Figure 10: Selected criteria plotted in the $f_d - \delta f_d$ parameter space: (a) A_N , (b) ΔI^{\max} , (c) P_i , (d) a , (e) V_f , and (f) τ_t . Observationally-constrained values, indicated by green areas of the colour scales, are given in Table 1. The size of the points is proportional to the magnetic Reynolds number and the CMB boundary conditions are shown by symbol shape. Symbols that have a black boundary lie within the Rm range that agrees with τ_{SV} . Each plot has a bounding polygon containing all simulations that match each criterion, shown in green.

the compliances, although low energy ratios tend to cluster at low f_d (see for instance Figure 9).

Figure 11(b) is the same as Figure 11(a) but with f_d and δf_d truncated at $L = 4$ to enable comparison with global paleofield models spanning millennial and longer timescales. Lowering L shifts the polygons and estimates of the field dipolarity to lower variability and higher dipolar fraction, though the specific simulations enclosed within each outline do not change. As with Figure 9, there is an exponential trend between a and f_d^4 , allowing us to estimate f_d^4 for 0.2-2.9 Ga timescales from the a values given in Biggin et al. (2020). As with f_d , the main region of overlap for f_d^4 polygons lies between the upper and lower dipolar fraction estimates from a , although the simulation matching the largest number (6) of criteria at once sits below this range ($f_d^4 = 0.63$ and $\delta f_d^4 = 0.199$). Geomagnetic field models built for < 10 kyr timescales (*gufm1* and *CALS10k.2*) have f_d^4 and δf_d^4 values that are comparable to some simulations. For similar f_d^4 , simulations have lower δf_d^4 than field models extending to longer timescales and including extreme events such as reversals and excursions. This suggests that reconciling simulation outputs with the range of geomagnetic field observations spanning multiple timescales requires either increasing the variability of moderate f_d dynamos or increasing the f_d of dynamos which are more variable.

6 Discussion and conclusions

We have found that simulations in our dataset generally do not simultaneously match all of the criteria we have considered to measure agreement between simulated and observed magnetic fields. Simulations with higher dipolarity and lower variability are more likely to match observed modern field morphology and short-timescale variability, while

simulations with lower dipolarity and greater variability are more likely to match criteria measuring the long-term variability of the field. The lack of overlap between the observations and geodynamo simulations through these criteria can be linked to three main types of limitations: (i) the geodynamo simulations, (ii) the observations and (iii) the construction of the criteria. We now discuss each of these in turn.

The geodynamo simulations used in this study employ control parameters that are still far from those of Earth's core. Some simulations access the strong-field regime that is often characterised by $E_m/E_k > 1$ (Schwaiger et al., 2019a) and can also reproduce values of Rm similar to those inferred from core flow inversions. However, while simulations that match individual criteria often have an Earth-like Rm and $E_m/E_k > 1$, simulations without these properties can also individually satisfy each criterion we have considered, except for τ_{SV} which varies with Rm . The main limitation of our simulations is that dipole fluctuations (and hence δf_d) are generally too small at the moderate dipolarity values recovered by field models. Several ways of addressing this limitation have been recently suggested: increasing Pr above the conventional value of 1 that has been used throughout this study (Jones and Tsang, 2025), adding weak stratification to strongly bottom-driven simulations (Aubert et al., 2025), and adding heterogeneous core-mantle boundary heat flow (Mound and Davies, 2023; Frasson et al., 2025). We believe that these effects, rather than continued sampling of a parameter space similar to that covered by the majority of our simulations, should be the focus of future studies.

Evaluating the criteria in simulations is also hampered by their finite duration. As discussed in Section 3, the majority of our simulations span < 3 magnetic diffusion times (the equivalent of $< 600,000$ years). Therefore they do not provide

Figure 11: Combined representation of results in Figure 10 in $f_d - \delta f_d$ parameter space for (a) $L = 12$ and (b) $L = 4$. Simulations included in this study are plotted in terms of their reversing properties and whether they lie in the Rm range that agrees with τ_{SV} . The vertical lines show the range of f_d estimated from a , the dipole-multipole transition and the f_d in 2025.0 calculated from the CHAOS-8 model. The 8 criteria considered are A_N , ΔI , P_1 , P_1^{max} , a , V_f , τ_t , and τ_{SV} . The lower panel also shows values from selected geomagnetic field models. The individual $L = 4$ polygons for panel (b) are shown in Figure A.3 in Appendix A.

a robust estimate of reversal frequency even if they do reverse. Clearly, the capacity of simulations to reverse on the timescale of 10 Myr covered by the Q_{PM} criteria is required for them to be considered Earth-like. However, the finite duration of simulations makes it difficult to assess this capacity. We believe these timescale factors may lead to lower scores of Q_{PM} diagnostics for some simulations than could be achieved if they were run longer, though this cannot be easily tested owing to the significant computational costs of spanning long timescales even at moderate E . On the other hand, including simulations with runtime < 0.5 magnetic diffusion times does not affect the observed trends for any metric we consider.

The observations used to build the criteria provide a heterogeneous spatio-temporal sampling of the true geomag-

netic field behaviour. We only have regularly spaced and spatio-temporally well located data for the modern era, limiting the ability to quantify the long term behaviour of the morphology and variability of the geomagnetic field. Producing observational quantities from the paleomagnetic measurements requires assumptions, and extreme field behaviour may be discarded as methodological limitation. Building these observations into time-dependent spherical harmonic geomagnetic field models reduces extreme behaviour further through smoothing and regularisation, requires further assumptions, and the resulting models provide limited resolution above spherical harmonic degree 4 and further back in time. We do not know how representative the modern magnetic field is of the geodynamo on geological timescales, making it difficult to apply statistics from

the present field or utilise dynamos that replicate the modern field within data assimilation for the paleofield. Thus, criteria that are built using these spherical harmonic field models will be fundamentally biased depending on the timescale they account for.

The criteria used in this study have been established to assess different aspects of geomagnetic field behaviour and their values can be estimated in various ways, with timescale emerging as an important factor. Quantities such as τ_{SV} and the compliance criteria rely on the existence of high-resolution field models, which are only available for the past 30 yrs for the former and 150 yrs for the latter. These quantities could be calculated for earlier epochs, but this requires accounting for the reduced spatio-temporal resolution of the observations. The values of such short-timescale criteria therefore inevitably change over time (e.g. Panovska et al., 2021; Wardinski et al., 2025), either because of intrinsic field changes or because of variations or improvements in available sampling. Furthermore, simulations generally span much longer timescales and thus generate ensembles of χ^2 and τ_{SV} , which can be summarised by various statistics (e.g. the minimum and median as used here; by windowing the time series (Mound et al., 2015)). Ultimately there is not a single way to perform comparisons on short timescales and the various choices that can be made will inevitably influence the results. On longer timescales it appears that there is some redundancy amongst the existing criteria. For example, V_f , a and P_i all vary approximately inversely with f_d . This is perhaps unsurprising since P_i combines variations of the virtual dipole moment and VGP latitude. Using summary statistics may introduce additional bias by equally summing misfit together (e.g. ΔQ_{PM} and χ^2) when the individual criteria are both correlated and not equally uncertain.

Despite the above limitations, a number of general conclusions arise from our work. We find that the dipolarity of the CMB field and its variability with time provide a useful parameter space for summarising and comparing results from a wide range of field criteria. Our simulations follow a general trend where dipolarity is inversely related to variability. The location on this trend where the individual criteria are met depends on the timescales they cover.

The level of agreement between simulated and observed fields differs significantly across the metrics we have considered. The morphological criteria Z_N , O_E , H_{FCF} and H_F are passed by the majority of our simulations and so are not discriminant of different physical conditions sampled by our simulations. The flux concentration factor F_C and latitudinal variation of VGP dispersion b are poorly constrained by observations and do not provide additional discriminatory power compared to the measures used in Figure 11. The criteria employed to determine agreement between simulations and observations will depend on the goal of a particular study (e.g. investigating rapid dynamics requires low E and hence short runtimes) and so it is possible that these deprecated ones are useful for purposes that are different from ours. However, to assess Earth-like behaviour on centennial to million-year timescales, we suggest that combinations of metrics measuring both short- and long-term field morphology and variability should be used. From presently available criteria these could be A_N , τ_{SV} , ΔI , and τ_t (or V_f), though future studies should also consider a more holistic approach to building criteria that span multiple spatial and temporal

scales (and hence available spatio-temporal resolution).

We find that f_d provides a good proxy for the variation of many criteria, specifically a , V_f , τ_t , median and maximum P_i and A_N . The magnetic Reynolds number is also an important diagnostic because it varies inversely with the SV timescale. There is no direct relation between metrics and the energy ratio E_m/E_k , though we find (as did Nakagawa and Davies (2022)) that simulations that tend to perform well according to the measures have $E_m/E_k > 1$. The greatest overlap between simulations matching disparate criteria occurs for median dipolarities in the range 0.5–0.64, which is substantially lower than the value of 0.71 for the modern geomagnetic field but is consistent with estimates inferred from long-term directional field variability through a . This reinforces the widespread perception that the dipolarity of the current geomagnetic field may be high compared to its long-term paleomagnetically derived average. This could have implications related to the dipole strength, which has been shown to be potentially weaker in the past than at the present (Wang et al., 2015). It also highlights a challenge for future geodynamo simulations, i.e. reproducing both a strongly dipolar magnetic field resembling the present-day at times while displaying large enough time variability to allow magnetic reversals.

While we have found that f_d and Rm are key factors in distinguishing Earth-like dynamos, there remains the difficulty in choosing the dynamo input parameters that will best reflect these values. For Rm this is straightforward since current direct numerical simulations can access Earth-like Rm while scaling laws adequately predict its variation with the control parameters (specifically the convective power, which can be related to E , Pr and Ra ; Aubert et al., 2017). f_d is more complicated and varies with many factors including the dynamo control parameters (E , Pm , Pr , Ra), the driving mode of convection, and the presence of heat-flow heterogeneity. Ongoing research could investigate how the driving mode of convection affects both f_d and each criterion. One potential avenue for future work is to consider a scaling for f_d based on the dipole-multipole transition. The challenge will be to move beyond inertially-driven reversals, which are well-characterised but not geophysically relevant (Tassin et al., 2021; Clarke et al., 2026), though developments in this direction are already underway (Aubert et al., 2025; Jones and Tsang, 2025).

Our dataset contains simulations with both thermally homogeneous and laterally varying core-mantle boundary conditions. We find no distinctive differences in the behaviour of these simulations when viewed through the lens of the criteria we have considered despite the expectation that both the morphology (Olson and Christensen, 2002; Aubert et al., 2007; Davies et al., 2008; Mound and Davies, 2023) and temporal variability (Christensen and Olson, 2003; Aubert et al., 2013; Korte et al., 2022) varies with the pattern and amplitude of imposed heterogeneity. We believe this is because the criteria we have considered do not explicitly measure the persistent deviations from longitudinal symmetry that are expected to be induced by the boundary heterogeneity (Gubbins, 2003; Biggin et al., 2026). Future studies seeking to identify the role of laterally-varying thermal heterogeneity on the geodynamo should focus on criteria that explicitly measure this effect.

Acknowledgements

We thank the two anonymous reviewers and Mathieu Dumberry, JSEDI editor, for their insightful feedback, which has improved the quality of this manuscript. HR and CD gratefully acknowledge Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) grant NE/V010867/1. SM and CD are supported by NERC grant NE/Y003500/1, and TF is supported by NERC grant NE/X014142/1. CC acknowledges joint NERC/CSEDI NSF grant EAR 2246758. We thank Jon Mound and Richard Bono for fruitful discussions about the hemispherical balance of flux and Quality of Paleomagnetic Modelling criteria. We thank everyone who originally ran the simulations included in this dataset, including Andy Biggin, Richard Bono, Andrew Clarke, Yael Engbers, David Gubbins, Simon Lloyd, Domenico Meduri, Jon Mound, Takashi Nakagawa, Souvik Naskar, and Ashley Willis. This work used the ARCHER2 UK National Supercomputing Service (<https://www.archer2.ac.uk>) and the Aire HPC system at the University of Leeds, UK.

Data availability

All data presented in this paper and plotting code can be found in the supplementary materials accompanying this manuscript (available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19188822>). The Gauss coefficients or dynamo statefiles will be made available by reasonable request.

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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Appendices

A Supplementary figures

A.1 Morphological compliance criteria wedge

In Figure A.1 we test the applicability of the $Rm - (E/Pm)$ wedge for all criteria in Figure 10. This parameter space was originally suggested in Figure 3 from Christensen et al. (2010). The simulations that fall within the wedge may either satisfy, as indicated by green on the colour bar, or fail the specific criterion.

Figure A.1: Criteria plotted on the $Rm - (E/Pm)$ wedge (grey dashed lines) proposed by Christensen et al. (2010): (a) A_N ; (b) ΔI^{max} ; (c) P_1 ; (d) a ; (e) V_f ; and (f) τ_t . The size of the points are proportional to f_d , and a black outline indicates simulations that lie within the Rm range that agrees with τ_{SV} . The core-mantle boundary conditions are marked by different symbols. Earth (as defined by Christensen et al. (2010)) is marked as a blue cross ($E/Pm = 5 \times 10^{-9}$, $Rm = 1200$).

A.2 Strong-field Agreement

The work from Nakagawa and Davies (2022) and Schwaiger et al. (2019a) suggest that the Earth should be in a MAC (Magnetic, Archimedean, Coriolis) balance with a magnetic to kinetic energy ratio greater than 1. In Figure A.2 we plot all criteria in Figure 10 in the f_d against E_m/E_k parameter space, as in Figure 2 in Nakagawa and Davies (2022). Most simulations lie above $E_m/E_k = 1$ and, therefore, should lie in the strong-field regime. Simulations with $E_m/E_k > 1$ and $0.35 < f_d < 0.75$ are more likely to match each criterion but there are also simulations within these ranges that do not meet the criterion.

Figure A.2: Criteria plotted on the $f_d - (E_m/E_k)$ parameter space proposed by Nakagawa and Davies (2022): (a) A_N ; (b) ΔI^{max} ; (c) P_1 ; (d) a ; (e) V_f ; and (f) τ_t . Dashed lines indicating bounds of f_d are taken from Davies et al. (2022). The size of the points are proportional to Rm , with those that match the τ_{SV} limits outlined in black. The core-mantle boundary conditions are marked by different symbols.

A.3 Polygons for f_d^4

In Figure A.3 we show the misfit of A_N , ΔI , P_1 , a , V_f and τ_t for ranges of f_d^4 and normalised variability (δf_d^4). This is the format as in Figure 10 but f_d^L truncated from $L = 12$ to $L = 4$. We draw bounding polygons containing all simulations that match each criterion. Owing to the limited number of simulations these polygons probably underestimate the region of $f_d^4 - \delta f_d^4$ space where each criterion is met, and they also contain simulations that do not meet the criterion.

Figure A.3: Selected criteria plotted in the $f_d^4 - \delta f_d^4$ parameter space: (a) A_N , (b) ΔI^{max} , (c) P_1 , (d) a , (e) V_f , and (f) τ_t . This plot is the same as Figure 10 but with the f_d^L values truncated at $L = 4$. Observationally-constrained values, indicated by green areas of the colour scales, are given in Table 1. The size of the points is proportional to magnetic Reynolds number and the CMB boundary conditions are shown by symbol shape. Symbols that have a black boundary lie within the Rm range that agrees with τ_{SV} . Each plot has a bounding polygon containing all simulations that match each criterion, shown in green.

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